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A Paradigm Shift - Work from Home to Work Energy Post Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

The pandemic taught us that a lot of job opportunities can be performed remotely which opened up new opportunities for both employers and employee. It has made a huge shift in considerations related to work-life balance. During pandemic employees have got a taste of what are the benefits of work from home and have more flexibility in terms of work-life balance and more control over their time and how they spend it. This research paper throws a light on the problems faced by the organisations in India when employees back to the office post pandemic. It will analyse the impact of this transition on the organisations and provide suggestions to improve the scenario.

Keywords: post pandemic, paradigm, work from home, work energy

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INTRODUCTION

The pandemic has taught us that many job opportunities can be pursued remotely, opening new opportunities for both employers and employees. It has fundamentally changed the way work-life balance is considered. Before pandemic work from home system was not popular in India. During the period of lockdown forcibly employees had to work from home and since then they tested the benefits of work from home.

Post pandemic everything is opened and firms called employees again to the workplace. But employees who learned the skills of work from home and maintaining work life balance are not willing to join the system again. India is likely to witness an 86% employee attrition for 2022, estimated by the recruitment agency Michael Page.

This has drawn the attention of researcher to study the benefits of work from home and thereby understands the reasons of attrition in India. The drawbacks of work from home help both employers

and employees to overcome the challenges and retain the skills.

OBJECTIVES

- To understand the pros and cons of work from home.
- To study the impact of transition from work from home to work life after pandemic.
- To provide suggestions to overcome the challenges.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study will help to understand the impact of transition from work from home to work life on organisation and employees. It will help the management to make this process smoother for employees from work from home to work life. It will help to reduce the attrition level and retain talent in company.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research paper is based on the secondary data. The data has been collected from websites, research papers etc. The data has been exhibited and analysed with help of a pie diagram.

Benefits of work from home:

Increase productivity:

Under work from home workers don't have to sit in traffic for hours every day, helps them to spend quality time with their family or pursue a hobby. With enough rest and free time each day, employees can better focus on their work, which directly increases the productivity and efficiency.

More freedom

In traditional work style worker is expected to work 8-9 hours a day in the office every week. They are not allowed to an hour-long nap because they can't focus on work. They can only do all this after work. On the contrary, workers are being given more freedom to organize their own working hours in work from

home. They can either work the early hours to free up the rest of the day or work through the nights. In case of work from home the focus is on getting the job done rather than spending a fixed number of hours in front of the laptop screen each day.

Improve employees well being

With no daily commutes, excessive coffee breaks, and long hours away from friends, family, and kids, it greatly improves employee well-being. Providing the best employee well-being creates a culture of high performance.

Reduce investment

Due to limited numbers of employees' presence at office there is no need of investing huge amount in building, office furniture and spending money on electricity and many other things.

Drawbacks of work from home

Aristotle said, "man is by nature a social animal; an individual who is unsocial naturally and not accidentally is either beneath our notice or more than human. Society is something that precedes the individual". It has been observed that humans are social animals. They can't live in isolation.

Create stress

Some of the employees may find it out difficult when to switch on and off official and personal life in case of work from home. It exhausts many of the employees mentally.

Reduce productivity

There are so many distractions outside the office environment. Taking a long hour nap, break may hamper some of the employees' productivity as it is a major distraction for the employees.

Lack of a good office environment

At home employees can't get a good office environment. They can't sit with team and have face

to face conversation which motivating them to set a higher goal and achieve it unitedly.

Issue of security

Transferring online data and documents might raise security issues. It requires a highly secured broadband network.

Impact of transition from work from home to work life after pandemic.

Aon Plc, global professional services firm has found that an attrition rate of 20.3% in India in the first of 2022 which is a significant increase after the two years lockdown.

There are numbers of factors such as compensation, growth opportunities, nature of work, pursuing higher education etc. compelled employees to leave the work place. One of the important causes of attrition is the transition from work from home to work life. Following is the employees' attrition data in the different sectors.

Graph 1.1
Sectorwise attrition

Above graph shows that major attrition is found in E-Commerce, IT enabled services, Information technology i.e. 28.7%, 21.4%, 21.5% respectively. It claims that sectors which demand the physical presence of employees are not affected more. But sectors which has a great scope of work from home affected a lot. Employees of these sectors have opted the jobs where the work from home became forever and allowed flexible working hours.

Employees had worked in isolation at home during pandemic. So once again joining to the office and socializing with others is the biggest challenge for the management and employees themselves. Maintaining hygiene is the priority of the organisations as employees were taking the utmost care of hygiene and safety at home.

Under the remote working Skype, Zoom, Google meet technologies were used to communicate with employees but it lost an emotional touch with others. Developing the bond and gaining the trust of employees once gain is the challenge for management as pandemic made their life unsure.

CONCLUSION

Different business sectors have the different requirements and accordingly work from home and work from office fit for them. During the pandemic, employees have had a taste of the benefits of working from home and have more flexibility in terms of work-life balance and more control over their time and how they spend it. Now it's a great challenge for the Indian firms to reduce the attrition rate and retain the talent in organisations.

Suggestions:

- Since last two years employees were at home and they became habitual of ambience, luxury and a healthy home environment. Thus, management must create a homely environment at work place which makes them comfortable and the transition becomes smoother.
- Management must develop a mind set of employees that work from office is inevitable in some of the sectors.
- Management must restructure the policies for employees related to recreation, compensation, facilities etc.

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